

Workpackage Design

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

Putting together your consortium's novel concept into a coherent and comprehensive workpackage structure is not self-evident. These tools can support this effort.

Benefits

These tools support you in translating your concept into a set of connected tasks.

Practical recommendations

Let's start off with the fact that there are many ways to get to a proper workpackage structure, prerequisite that your consortium already has at least a rough outline of the concept. Getting there efficiently and practicing MAA, that is a challenge.

Often the time to get here is limited, and you will have to decide whether time or participation prevails. Below you will find a "Fast Track" recommendation in case of time pressure, as well as an Extended Approach.

Fast Track

Are you in a hurry? We recommend the GIST method. The method gets you quickly from overarching goals to necessary tasks. Please note that dependencies between tasks are not extracted through this approach, and to mediate the associated risks it is recommended to accompany the exercise above with a RAID assessment. Once an overview of activities have been generated it becomes time to divide the work across the consortium, which can be done through filling out a RACI matrix. If you need more detailed breakdown of the projects activities (tasks) and the required in- and outputs you could employ Programme Logic across all defined activities. Still too many activities, or maybe short on budget? Please try plotting all activities across a Effort x Value graph to help prioritize across the workpackages.

Please note that this method is quick, but not inherently MAA appropriate. It does not naturally allow for much participation from your diverse consortium members. It is highly recommended to think critically about participation across these exercises and invite partners whenever possible!

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Transparent communication about agenda's, expectations, and results

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

GIST

RAID

RACI

Programme Logic

Effort x Value

Trajectories of Change

Future Radars

What, Who, Why, When, How?

**right click to open*

Extended Approach

If you have planned for more time, and a deeper investment into your future consortium's ability to work together and share responsibility in the tasks, we recommend replacing some of the previous exercises. Specifically, replacing the GIST with either the EIT Climate KIC **Trajectories of Change** or **Future Radars** exercise. While it can still be useful to make a RAID assessment to identify potential risks, the other factors will naturally become apparent in these two exercises. Additionally, replacing the RACI matrix with a What, Who, Why, When, How? exercise will not only make the process more participatory, but it also crucially enhances the ownership across the consortium.

Additional Noteworthy Mentions:

- The "Communities of Practice Playbook" contains several good chapters within this context, specifically Leadership and Collaboration and Cooperation.
- If your consortium is still split on certain concept/content aspects Outcome Spaces from the Integrated Research Toolkit could potentially help find consensus.